

Can an average American afford housing in 2021?

Fig. 1 Median home prices

Fig. 2 Monthly mortgage payment

Fig. 3 Average american salary estimate

Fig. 4 Mortgage percentage salary after taxes

Result

Compared to the South/Midwest, Coastal & densely populated areas are increasingly unaffordable to average Americans due to gentrification, location and disproportionate pay increase compared to housing prices.

Model Type: Linear Regression

Number of Regressions Calculated: ~3,140

Country: United States

PopulationBinSize: County

Analysis Breakun: Per Countv

Accepted on March 9, 2024 (see peer reviews)

Primary Author

Franco Sanchez Torres

Contributing Authors

Parth Shrivastava Rahul Singh

In-depth analysis at a county-level showed disproportionate housing prices across America, upon conducting comparative analysis with the median take-away salary per county, patterns began to emerge. Gentrification and urbanization have lead overpopulation in coastal areas, leading to a competitive and oversaturated job market, this has led to a disproportionate spike in housing prices compared to salary which has plateaued in comparison.

Other contributing factors include largely state or privately owned land; boosting home prices, large tourist income (seasonal revenue), or extremely high tax rates. Notable examples of “unaffordable” counties include Nantucket, Brooklyn, Central California.

On the other hand, counties in the Midwest and south have considerably low population density, leaving large swathes of land unoccupied. It is unsurprising remote locations have the most affordable homes, expenses would stay relatively low for the same reasons listed above, just the opposite effect.

Furthermore, there were some interesting abnormalities to note. Southern states with jobs in the mining and oil industries offered very high salaries in areas with minimal expenses and low rental costs. This led to certain “bubble” counties where the median take-home salary was significantly higher compared to home prices, causing an inverse of the effect on major urban counties.

A few notable statistics from the analysis and data set are included below for reference.

List of the counties with the highest monthly mortgage payment of Q2 2021:

1. New York County, New York: \$4,656
2. Nantucket County, Massachusetts: \$4,625
3. San Mateo County, California: \$4,535
4. Santa Clara County, California: \$4,505
5. San Francisco County, California: \$4,476

List of the counties with the lowest monthly mortgage payment of Q2 2021:

1. Todd County, South Dakota: \$110
2. Malette County, South Dakota: \$135
3. McDowell County, West Virginia: \$143
4. Kent County, Texas: \$150
5. King County, Texas: \$158

List of the counties with the highest median home price of Q2 2021:

1. New York County, New York: \$1,227,108
2. Nantucket County, Massachusetts: \$1,218,781
3. San Mateo County, California: \$1,195,275
4. Santa Clara County, California: \$1,187,214
5. San Francisco County, California: \$1,179,676

List of the counties with the lowest median home price of Q2 2021:

1. Todd County, South Dakota: \$28,896
2. Malette County, South Dakota: \$35,675
3. McDowell County, West Virginia: \$37,684
4. Kent County, Texas: \$39,652
5. King County, Texas: \$41,578

References

[1] McMullen, Troy. “Why Homes on Nantucket, Massachusetts, Are Reeling in the Rich.” *Subscribe to Read | Financial Times*, Financial Times, 14 Oct. 2016, <https://www.ft.com/content/adc0dc92-8ba9-11e6-8cb7-e7ada1d123b1>.

[2] “Nantucket, MA.” *Data USA*, <https://datausa.io/profile/geo/nantucket-ma/#economy>.

[3] “How Much Does a House on Nantucket Cost?” *Fisher Real Estate Nantucket*, 28 Nov. 2022, <https://fishernantucket.com/how-much-does-a-house-in-nantucket-cost/>.

[4] Mirror, The Inquirer and. “Conservation Foundation Launches Summer Wellness Series.” *Inquirer and Mirror*, Inquirer and Mirror, 18 June 2021, <https://www.ack.net/stories/conservation-foundation-launches-summer-wellness-series,24821>.

[5] “Mining Royalties in Eureka and Lander Could Solve Rural Problems.” *The Nevada Independent*, 24 Aug. 2021, <https://thenevadaindependent.com/article/mining-royalties-in-elko-and-lander-could-solve-rural-problems>.

[6] NV Energy, <https://www.nvenergy.com/about-nvenergy/economic-development/counties/eureka>.

[7] “Eureka County, NV.” *Data USA*, <https://datausa.io/profile/geo/eureka-county-nv>.

[8] “Upton County.” *TSHA*, <https://www.tshaonline.org/handbook/entries/upton-county>.

[9] “Estimate of Median Household Income for Upton County, TX.” *FRED*, 21 Dec. 2022, <https://fred.stlouisfed.org/series/MHITX48461A052NCEN>.

[10] PBRPC Programs - Economic Development - Upton County Profile. http://www.pbrpc.org/economic_development_county_upton.php.

Protocols

- [1] Data Analytics Project codebase
- [2] Free Paycheck Calculator: Hourly & Salary Take Home after Taxes

Data sets

- [1] Data Analytics Project dataset
- [2] National Association of Realtors Housing Statistics by county
- [3] U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis (BEA)